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AZERBAIJAN, POLAND, AND UKRAINE COOPERATION IN THE INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC PROJECT "SARMATIA"

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Abstract

The project of the Eurasian Oil Corridor, designed to transport oil from the Caspian Sea region to Western and Central Europe via the Odessa-Brody-Plosk-Gdansk oil pipeline to the port of Wilhelmshaven (Northwest Germany), was of great importance at the beginning of the 21st century.

In January 2008, the Azerbaijani State Oil Company, the Georgian "Oil and Gas Corporation", and the Lithuanian company "Klaipeda Nafta" joined the Polish-Ukrainian joint consortium created on the basis of the Polish pipeline company "Sarmatia". According to the contract, the construction was planned to be completed in 2011 and 40 million tons of Caspian oil would be exported to Europe per year.

Pipeline Odessa-Brody was planned as an alternative route for transporting Caspian oil to Europe through Ukraine and Poland. Bypassing Russian territory, the pipeline was supposed to enter the Polish refineries in Plock and Gdansk. Oil was supposed to be delivered from the Baltic Sea coast, Gdansk to Central and Western European countries. It should be noted that the main 250 infrastructure projects announced by the European Commission as "common interests of the European Union in the field of energy" included the construction of the Odessa-Brody pipeline to Poland (Adamov point). \$6 billion was allocated for the implementation of this project.

At the summits, the heads of the states prepared a comprehensive review, conducted a financial analysis, considered route options, and discussed a promising economic model of the project, capacities, and possibilities of using new oil and gas enterprises in Poland and Ukraine.

Polish support for the project would lead to the emergence of a huge transport artery in Europe that would transport oil from Asia to Europe, Scandinavia to Poland, and Ukraine. One of the reasons the prospects for the project's development seemed hopeless, along with the huge investment demand, was the obvious and hidden resistance of Russia, which supplied its oil to Europe through Soviet pipelines.

Despite the measures and plans a number of countries expressed on the new energy project, it has not given any positive result and has only been reflected in documents and speeches. This paper evaluates the preparation of the "Sarmatia" pipeline project, which has an important meaning for the EU energy supply, examines the attitude of the participating countries, and argues the reasons for its failure.

Keywords: international project, economic cooperation, oil export to Europe, Odessa-Brody- Plosk-Gdansk, Azerbaijani oil

Introduction The gradual complication of the extraction of natural resources and the soaring demand for energy creates crucial problems for the modern world. It is obvious that energy shortage will have an extremely negative impact on all countries, regardless of their level of economic development. The situation is particularly complicated for the European Union, as the EU is forced to import nearly 60% of its energy resources. The researchers confirm that if the problem of reliable energy sources is not solved, the situation may become more challenging, and the import of the necessary energy resources may reach 70%. Therefore, in the countries of the European Union, much attention is paid not only to the issue of providing energy resources but also to energy-saving technologies and the development of renewable energy sources (Bolshaya Yevropa, 2014, 279-280). In September 2015, the UN Supreme Assembly adopted a document that reflects the goals of creating the necessary conditions for the sustainable development of the well-being of all people. One of the main conditions for achieving these goals was a modern energy supply as

economic, social, and technological progress is impossible without the energy supply (OON, 15 sentyabr, 2015). Energy policy has been one of the most important issues of the European Union for a long time. Energy security is now become a global priority for world politics and the economy.

The circumstances of the late 20th-early 21st century have shown that the fuel and energy complex is not only a national factor for the economic development of Azerbaijan but also an effective means of interstate economic and political cooperation. Already at the end of the 20th century, the first projects to unite oil and gas producers in the Caspian Sea basin began to be implemented. The project of the Eurasian Oil Corridor, designed to transport oil from the Caspian Sea region to Western and Central Europe via the Odessa-Brody-Plosk-Gdansk oil pipeline to the port of Wilhelmshaven (Northwest Germany), was of great importance at the beginning of the 21st century. At the summits, the heads of the states prepared a comprehensive review, conducted a financial analysis, considered route options, and discussed a promising

economic model of the project, capacities, and possibilities of using new oil and gas enterprises in Poland and Ukraine (Aliyev, 2010,169). Despite the measures and plans several countries expressed on the new energy project, it has not given any positive result and has only been reflected in documents and speeches. This paper evaluates the preparation of the “Sarmatia” pipeline project which has an important meaning for the EU energy supply, examines the attitude of the participating countries, and argues the reasons for its failure.

Materials and methods There are few studies on the subject. N.Aliyev, Mariush Patey, Z.Mammadov, R.Ibragimov, A. Moldovan, M.Gonchar, O. Turuk have paid attention to several aspects of the topic including the capacity of the Azerbaijani natural resources, Poland-Ukraine relations as well as social and economic circumstances in the region. In his “Oil and oil aspect in the 21st century’s Azerbaijani economy,” Natig Aliyev, a former head of the State Oil Company of Azerbaijan Republic (SOCAR) touched on several issues of cooperation of Azerbaijan with various countries in the field of energy resources. The study also emphasized the importance of implementing the Eurasian Oil Transport Corridor. The author points out three planned stages for the implementation of the project (Aliyev, 2010). Mammadov studies Azerbaijan's interest in alternative ways of energy resources transportation including the Odessa-Brody oil pipeline. The author insists that alternative routes of transportation of energy resources to world markets will allow the country to pursue a more independent foreign policy, ensuring its national security (Mamedov, 2012, p.124).

A Ukrainian researcher named Dudnik has brought to light some noteworthy developments regarding the Odesa-Brody oil pipeline. Specifically, there has been a shift in the pipeline's function from reverse mode to averse mode, and work on extending the pipeline to Plock, Poland is still ongoing (Dudnik, 2010). After analyzing the regional trends related to the project, Moldovan pointed out that the Ukrainian political elites failed to consider several crucial geopolitical factors. (Moldovan, 2006). According to Gonchar, the shift to reverse mode was a result of the Kremlin's influence and aligned with Russia's energy objectives (Gonchar, 2013). Turuk analyzes the significance of the Odessa-Brody oil pipeline for the region by examining the official visits of President Viktor Yushchenko to Azerbaijan and Prime Minister Viktor Yanukovich to Poland in 2006 (Truk, 2006). This research employs a comparative analysis.

Results and discussion. At the start of the 21st century, the economic partnership between Azerbaijan and Poland was not particularly successful. Although there was strong political cooperation, the trade of goods between the two nations was unsatisfactory. Over a ten-year period from 2002-2012, the trade only amounted to \$8-112 million (Gomolka, 2015). The leaders of Poland have shown support for Azerbaijan's bid to join the World Trade Organization (WTO) and have expressed willingness to encourage other countries to vote in favor of Azerbaijan. Poland's

political leaders highlighted the benefits of WTO membership, citing how foreign direct investments flooded into the country after it joined in 1995. This resulted in a smooth transition of Poland's economy from socialism to a market-based system. To further boost economic growth, direct investment and commodity exchange should be increased.

Poland took an active approach towards developing a neighborhood policy in Europe after becoming a member of the European Union. This was done on behalf of the organization, as stated by Chernova (2016, 54). In the Sejm's annual reports of the Ministers of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Poland, it was noted that on May 26, 2008, during a meeting of the Council of the European Union on General Issues and External Relations, Polish Foreign Minister Radoslaw Sikorski and the Swedish representative proposed the creation of the Eastern Partnership. This program aimed to establish political and economic cooperation with six countries of the former USSR, namely Ukraine, Moldova, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, and Belarus. Despite the fact that the proposal was not immediately accepted by the member states, on May 7, 2009, at the summit of the heads of state of the EU, as well as at the meeting of the “Eastern Cooperation” in Prague, the establishment was officially announced (Staszak, 2009).

Poland has business relationships with numerous EU countries and is exploring new markets. Azerbaijan's markets are of interest to Poland, and the country participated in a program to regulate Azerbaijan's agricultural legislation. Poland provided assistance to Azerbaijan in improving its economic legal system. The Polish Investment Promotion Agency (PYTA) and the Azerbaijan Export and Investment Promotion Fund (Azpromo) have held several meetings to strengthen economic ties and increase investments between the two countries.

In the 1st century BC, the Danube River flowed all the way to the Caspian coast of Azerbaijan. The project had an important mission and aimed at the modernization of the existing constructions and the definition of their implementation rather than the construction of the new facilities. The main part of the project was the “Druzhba” oil trunk pipeline, the Baku-Supsa oil pipeline (WREP, Western RouteExport pipeline), and the Odessa-Brody oil pipeline directly adjacent to the Southern Arm of “Druzhba”.

In February 1993, President L. Kravchuk made the decision to construct the start-up section of the Odessa-Brody pipeline, which would transport Caspian oil to Ukraine. The project was fully funded by Ukraine and took five years to complete, costing \$453 million. The pipeline spans 667 km in length and has an annual capacity of 14.5 million tons. In 2001, the pipeline connecting the Pivdenny terminal near Odessa to Brody in the Lviv region was finished with the support of Western countries. The Odessa-Brody Business Plan was economically justified and developed in 2003 by the well-known consulting and auditing company PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC). The construction investments reached \$500 million. Bringing the pipeline to Plock would have necessitated over 780

thousand tons of technical oil. PwC experts found it essential to transport Caspian oil through the pipeline for Europe. However, European business owners were unprepared to support the project. Eastern European oil refining firms, particularly Polish companies, found Caspian oil costly and were unwilling to allocate significant financial resources to it. According to Argus agency, the price of Caspian oil at the Adamova Zastava point in Brody, on the border of Poland, is \$35 per ton more expensive than Russian Ural oil. In 2003, Ukraine, Poland, and the European Union signed an agreement for Poland to construct an oil pipeline through its territory, which would transport oil to the Plock refinery and then to the port of Gdansk on the Baltic Sea coast. Despite Polish officials stating that the pipeline would be extended to Plock, where a large oil refinery is situated, Poland did not invest in the construction of the Brody-Plock pipeline. Consequently, the pipeline has been unused for a considerable period.

Ukraine yielded to Russian pressure and abandoned a project that was deemed inefficient. Instead, they declared their intention to transport Russian oil to the Black Sea using an existing pipeline. The pipeline would operate in reverse mode, which meant that the oil would be delivered to the Yuzhny offshore oil terminal for loading onto tankers, rather than being available for Eastern European countries. This decision caused a significant amount of controversy and resulted in numerous protests in Ukraine, as it contradicted the original intent of the project. Since Ukraine could not sign a contract with Europeans willing to buy Azerbaijani oil, it had to accept Russia's offer. The Orange Revolution of 2004-2005 crucially changed the destination of oil pipelines. The new export route (Odessa-Brody) served the interests of Russia. Ukrainian President Leonid Kuchma explained his decision with national interests and the multi-vector nature of Kyiv's policy.

In July 2005, the European Commission organized a tender for the "Project of Odessa-Brody oil pipeline extension to Poland," and the international company "SWECO pic-ISF-Cantor" won the bid. The business plan for the EU-funded Odessa-Brody-Plotsk project was completed in 2006, confirming the implementation and potential competitiveness of the Caspian oil route. Despite European interest in this alternative route, Ukrtransnafta was unable to ensure shipment.

In 2007, the first Energy Summit took place in Krakow under the leadership of Polish President Lech Kaczynski. In a joint official statement, the Presidents of Azerbaijan, Georgia, Lithuania, Poland, and Ukraine, along with the Special Representative of Kazakhstan, expressed their support for the Euro-Asian Oil Transportation Corridor (EAOTC) project. Later that year, at the second Energy Summit in Vilnius, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Ukraine, Poland, and Lithuania signed an agreement to create a joint venture responsible for designing and constructing the Baku-Odessa-Brody-Plock-Gdansk oil pipeline. Subsequently, at a working group meeting of 'Sarmatia' members held in November 2007 at the Yuzhny oil terminal (Odessa region), representatives

from five oil companies, Azerbaijan, Ukraine, Poland, Lithuania, and Georgia, addressed several critical issues related to their future activities. They agreed to convene the next meeting of the working group of the International Oil Pipeline Company "Sarmatia" in December 2007 in the Polish city of Wroclaw to discuss technical aspects of the business plan.

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Pipeline Odessa-Brody was planned as an alternative route for transporting Caspian oil to Europe through Ukraine and Poland. Bypassing the Russian territory the pipeline was supposed to enter the Polish refineries in Plock and Gdansk. Oil was supposed to be delivered from the Baltic Sea coast, Gdansk to the countries of Central and Western Europe. It should be noted that the main 250 infrastructure projects announced by the European Commission as "common interests of the European Union in the field of energy" included the construction of the Odessa-Brody pipeline to Poland (Adamov point). \$6 billion was allocated for the implementation of this project. According to the European Commission, "projects of common interest" would enjoy improved procedural and regulatory conditions with licensing, and also receive financial support from the United European Fund. It is noteworthy that 5.85 billion euro were allocated from the fund for the trans-European energy structure from 2014 to 2020. The pipeline was supposed to combine the Ukrainian pipeline with the Polish oil system to transport Caspian oil to Eastern Europe. The length of the pipeline was to be 317 km with 30 million tons maximum capacity. The total material costs of the Odessa-Brody-Plock project were estimated at 455 million euros. The construction of the Ukrainian side was 125 km, and the Polish side was 270 km. (ZN,UA, 2013).

On May 23, 2008, at the third Energy Summit in Kiev, the Presidents of Azerbaijan, Georgia, Lithuania, Poland, and Ukraine jointly announced the imminent completion of the construction of the Euro-Asian Oil Transport Corridor and the start of transportation of Caspian energy raw materials along the specified route. At the fourth Energy Summit in Baku in November 2008, the participants once again stressed the importance of connecting the Odessa-Brody oil pipeline to the Euro-Asian system, transporting crude oil to Europe. Speaking at the summit, Georgian President Mikheil Saakashvili expressed his concern about Russia's monopolist behavior on energy resources. Ukrainian President Viktor Yushchenko noted the importance of political will for the implementation of the Odessa-Brody-Gdansk project [MUSAVAT, 2008].

The aggravation of relations between Moscow and Kiev in 2010 led to the termination of the route in the

opposite direction (Brody-Odessa). Until 2010, the pipeline operated in reverse mode, delivering Russian oil to the Odessa refinery. In mid-2010, the operation of the pipeline in this mode was stopped, the pipeline was loaded with technical oil of Azerbaijan, and Caspian crude oil began to be supplied to the Mozyr oil Refinery. Thus, Belarus was only country that used the Sarmatia project at that time. Belarus actually did not join the project initially. However, due to "oil war" between Belarus and Russia, former urgently needed energy resources. Instead of the planned 4 million barrels, only 1 million barrels were loaded into the pipeline. When the conflict between two neighboring countries was over Belarus preferred cheap Russian oil (Yusubov, 2011, 8).

The meeting in Krakow with the participation of five countries (Poland, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Lithuania, Ukraine) on the Odessa-Brody-Gdansk gas pipeline caused discussions about Russia's negative attitude. It could be assumed that Russia would create serious problems for implementation of the project that provides transportation of the Caspian oil to Europe bypassing Russian territory., Jan Pera, an expert on Eastern Europe also expressed his concern about Russian attitudes toward a new project. The Polish press closely watched Putin's reaction to the discussions about the Odessa-Brody-Gdansk pipeline. The urgent agreement of the three countries (Russia, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan) on the Turkmen gas supply through Kazakhstan to Russia in some cases considered as Putin's response to the project (TREND, 2011; Mammadli, 2023, p.9). It should be noted that the Jan Pera's opinions have largely justified. Soon Ukraine withdrew from the project under the influence of Russia calling the project ineffective and stating that the pipeline will be used for transportation of the Russian oil. The energy security expert John Roberts claims that it is possible to imagine pipelines that will bypass Russia and enter Western markets, but it will be a very complex project in political, technical and financial terms. It means that any energy project will be successful if Russia participates in it, otherwise serious obstacles will be created by Russia (KAZAKHSTAN TODAY, 2007). Putin's sudden visit to Central Asia was interpreted as pressure on the President of Kazakhstan Nursultan Nazarbayev. Nazarbayev postponed his visit to Krakow subsequently and Deputy Minister of Energy of the republic represented Kazakhstan in Poland. His cautious statements in Krakow about the Odessa-Brody-Gdansk project prove Russia's negative role (BBC AZERİ.COM, 2007). Polish scholar Mariusz Patey argues that Azerbaijan was the first country that supported the oil pipeline project to Europe without the participation of Russia and participated in all meetings related to the project. However, the political leadership of Kazakhstan couldn't demonstrate such kind of position refusing any actions against the interests of Russia (Patey, 2021).

In July 2011, after signing documents on cooperation between Azerbaijan and Poland, Polish President Boris Komorowski, speaking at a press conference, noted that Poland is ready to participate in the transportation of energy resources, and this issue is

important not only for two countries but also for the European Union. Recalling the Odessa-Brody-Plock-Gdansk project that was approved by the European Union, the Polish President also drew attention to the increasing commercial value of the project. Answering questions about the Odessa-Brody-Plock-Gdansk pipeline, the President acknowledged that Poland supports the project politically. Komorowski also stressed the importance of the accurate business plan of the project and preliminary calculation of its capacity. The President emphasized that the supply of one million tons of Azerbaijani oil per year to Polish-invested refineries is an important breakthrough. He also noted the necessity of solving the energy problems of the region as soon as possible (APRIS, 2011).

The project of the Eurasian Oil Transportation Corridor is of great importance for Poland. The project creates an additional way of oil transportation to Polish refineries, it increases the energy security of Poland and the entire region. At the same time the project provides extra revenues to the Polish budget. The leaders of the Polish company explained the prospects of the project by technical and economic conditions, the situation in the international arena and the lifting of the embargo on oil exports from Iran.

In September 2013, the Regional Environmental Protection Authority in Lublin (Poland) issued an environmental consent for the construction of the Brody-Plock oil pipeline taking into account the possibility of transporting oil to Gdansk and further west. However, on the same days, the Polish government stated that Poland was not sure about the prospects of the project. It was the complete opposite of Poland's initial position concerning the project. When the discussions started around the pipeline, Poland expected other countries to join the project. However, caution for political reasons also existed. Meanwhile, Polish scholar Mariusz Patey has a distinctive explanation for Poland's approach. Patey claims that the Polish ruling circles are concerned about the reduction of Russian oil exports which would consequently affect the price of crude oil offered to Polish refineries. It was taken into account that Russian oil producers also invest in oil refineries in different countries. These causes, unfortunately, badly affected the fate of the project (Patey, 2021). Although Azerbaijan, Ukraine, Georgia, Lithuania and Poland tried to reduce Russia's influence in the energy sector, it is clear that Moscow still has efficient mechanisms of control over the region.

In May and August 2013, the 495 million zloty (or 120 million euros) allocated for the Odessa-Brody project was spent for the country's gas pipelines by the Polish government. The Polish Ministry of Economy explained that the country couldn't lose the financial assistance provided by the Council of Europe for the country's energy security (*Ekonomicheskaya pravda*, 2013).

The question of restoration of the Odessa-Brody pipeline that remained without oil for five years re-appeared on the agenda of Baku and Kyiv in 2014. Ukraine was interested in strengthening its position as a guarantor of European energy security. However, the

logistics of oil exports from Azerbaijan to Europe via Ukraine is a very complex process. First, oil is to be delivered from Baku to the Pivdenniy terminal through the Georgian port of Supsa by tankers. After the arrival of crude oil in Brody, transportation is to be carried out by rail to Polish refineries. It was planned to increase the volume of crude oil exported via the Baku-Supsa pipeline from 7 million to 9 million tons per year. The transportation costs were significant and made the route inefficient if compared to Russian Ural oil that was exported through "Druzhba" pipeline. Poland was not interested in financing the Brody-Plotsk pipeline. EU was ready to cover all expenditures however, there was no guarantee of loading the pipeline.

In June 2016, during the meeting of the President of Ukraine Petro Poroshenko with the President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, an agreement was reached on the restoration of the Odessa-Brody project. Aliyev has announced that Azerbaijan exports large volumes of oil to the European market and has become a transit country for countries located on the eastern coast of the Caspian Sea. In this regard, the restoration of the project may open up new opportunities. Although Azerbaijan began to make plans for the restoration of the project, some difficulties have led to the delay of the planned activities. Azerbaijan was busy with financing the "Southern Gas Pipeline", which was estimated at \$40 billion. Baku's share in this project was \$13 billion, and Azerbaijan already began negotiations with international financial organizations on granting a loan.

The statements of the Presidents of Ukraine and Azerbaijan dated July 14, 2016, on the resumption of the Odessa-Brody-Plock oil pipeline project were positively rated by Poland. Warsaw expressed its high expectations from Baku and Kyiv. This was reported by the Polish company in response to a request from Ukrinform. However, no agreement was reached on filling the pipeline with Azerbaijani oil and financing the Brody-Plosk pipeline construction. Meanwhile, the joint statements of the leaders of Ukraine and Azerbaijan were analyzed in the Russian press, and called unpromising. It was circulated that in conditions of intense competition, it will be impossible to find investors and suppliers for an inefficient transit pipeline (PRAYM, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Implementing the "Sarmatia" project crucially depends on serious political, economic, and social issues that connected participant countries and consumers of the European Union and the Russian Federation. The incompleteness of the project that was supported by the European Union has several reasons. The long-term Russian-Ukrainian tension has proved that it is impossible to reach political independence without achieving energy independence. Therefore, at the first stage of independence, Ukraine attempted an energy revolution, the main goal of which was to achieve diversification of energy sources. Combining one of the Ukrainian national projects - the "Odessa-Brody" with the "Druzhba" pipeline that transports oil to Central and Southern Europe, would open up the southern direction and create ample opportunities for

sending energy carriers (Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Iran and Iraq, Libya) to Ukraine.

Polish support for the project would lead to the emergence of a huge transport artery in Europe that would transport oil from Asia to Europe, Scandinavia to Poland and Ukraine. One of the reasons why the prospects for the development of the project seemed hopeless, along with the huge investment demand, was the obvious and hidden resistance of Russia, which supplied its oil to Europe through Soviet pipelines. Relations between Russia and European countries have historically been complicated and contradictory. In this sense, relations with the former socialist republics, especially with Poland, which supported anti-Russian alliances in the post-Soviet space, have become strained.

At the project's first stage, consumer countries like Slovakia, the Czech Republic, and Hungary voted in favor of the pipeline. Nevertheless, they have not demonstrated readiness to sign the contract. Although the information about the pipeline was widely discussed in Azerbaijani, Polish and Ukrainian media and attracted the interest of Iran (after the lifting of sanctions) and the United States, the project that initially was anti-Russian could live up to all expectations.

What were the expectations from the "Sarmatia" project? The composition of the participant countries and their market orientation have great importance for EU energy security. The project demonstrated the possibilities of an alternative energy source for European consumers that depend on the Russian market for a long time. The project created excellent opportunity for oil refineries that do not have access to the sea. Azerbaijani oil company SOCAR would get new consumers and an efficient transport corridor. Thus, these opportunities would weaken the position of the Russian Federation as a giant oil supplier in the region and would allow consumers to negotiate on more favorable terms. The countries that were interested in the project have large energy sources, valid pipeline infrastructure, as well as financial capabilities. All these opportunities betrayed confidence in the successful completion of the project. However, the appearance of a new supplier, the Azerbaijani SOCAR in the region could not serve the interests of the monopolist Russian pipeline "Transneft", as well as Russian oil companies that supply oil to refineries in Poland, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Germany.

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